

Environment-Induced Phase Modulation of Threshold Resonances in Low-Energy D+D Nuclear Reactions

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Low-energy D + D reactions in condensed matter environments exhibit several anomalous features, including suppression of the neutron channel, enhanced angular anisotropy, plateau-like yield behavior, and non-monotonic time evolution of the enhancement factor. These observations cannot be consistently described within conventional models based solely on static electron screening.

In this work, we present a phase-sensitive framework in which the reaction cross section arises from the coherent superposition of direct and resonant contributions. We show that environment-induced phase modifications lead to a distribution of effective resonance energies, even for an intrinsically narrow near-threshold 0^+ state.

Within this framework, the effective resonance condition itself becomes environment dependent through phase variations of the scattering amplitude. As a result, the experimentally observed cross section corresponds to a superposition of locally shifted resonant contributions, leading to an apparent broadening without requiring a large intrinsic decay width.

We find that a consistent description of experimental data is obtained only when both the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier are modified in a correlated, environment-dependent manner. In particular, the model reproduces the low-energy enhancement observed in Pd targets and explains the limitations of screening-only descriptions below ~ 2 keV.

The time-dependent evolution of the enhancement factor provides an independent test of the framework. The observed non-monotonic behavior is reproduced when phase evolution is included, indicating that the reaction dynamics are governed by a dynamically evolving interference structure.

These results indicate that low-energy nuclear reactions in condensed matter require a phase-sensitive, environment-dependent description that extends beyond the conventional static screening picture.

I. INTRODUCTION

Deuteron–deuteron (D + D) fusion reactions at low energies play a central role in nuclear physics, nuclear astrophysics, and fusion science. As one of the simplest few-body nuclear systems, the D + D reaction provides a unique testing ground for fundamental aspects of the nucleon–nucleon interaction, few-body dynamics, and symmetry properties of the strong force [1, 2]. Owing to its relatively simple structure, it has been widely used to benchmark theoretical descriptions of light nuclear systems and reaction mechanisms.

In astrophysical environments, D + D reactions contribute to energy generation and nucleosynthesis processes in dense stellar and sub-stellar systems, where reaction rates are strongly influenced by plasma effects and many-body interactions [3, 4]. These conditions make low-energy fusion reactions particularly sensitive to modifications of the effective interaction potential.

Beyond astrophysics, D + D reactions are also of considerable importance for controlled fusion research and advanced energy applications [5, 6]. In particular, the low-energy regime represents a critical domain where the interplay between nuclear structure, reaction dynamics, and environmental effects becomes increasingly significant.

Low-energy nuclear reactions in condensed matter systems have attracted sustained attention over the past

decades, driven by persistent experimental observations of reaction yields exceeding expectations based on bare nucleus interactions. These enhancements are commonly attributed to electron screening, whereby the Coulomb barrier between reacting nuclei is effectively reduced by the surrounding electron cloud. Within this conventional picture, the reaction energy is shifted as $E \rightarrow E + U_e$, leading to an increased tunneling probability [7, 8].

While this approach successfully describes a broad range of data at moderate energies, several experiments performed at very low energies reveal systematic deviations from this simple description. In particular, the enhancement factor often exhibits a nontrivial energy dependence, including saturation, flattening, or even slight increases toward lower energies. Such behavior cannot be consistently reproduced within a model based solely on a constant screening potential, indicating that additional mechanisms must contribute to the reaction dynamics in this regime [9–13].

A number of theoretical approaches have been developed to describe low-energy D + D reactions, including R -matrix, T -matrix, and DWBA-based formulations [14–16]. These frameworks successfully reproduce cross sections and angular distributions under standard conditions, particularly for reactions in gaseous targets [17–19]. However, experimental studies in metallic environments at very low energies have revealed several anomalies, including deviations in the neutron-proton branching ratio

and enhanced angular anisotropy, which cannot be fully explained within these conventional approaches [16, 42]. In particular, DWBA calculations, which account only for direct reaction mechanisms, fail to reproduce the observed behavior, indicating the importance of resonance contributions beyond the direct reaction picture. This limitation has been noted in earlier studies, where discrepancies between DWBA predictions and experimental data pointed to the role of threshold resonance effects and isospin mixing [16].

Early investigations of these anomalies attributed them to the influence of near-threshold resonances and isospin mixing in the compound nucleus, providing partial explanations of the observed angular distributions and branching ratios [14, 16, 20]. Subsequent studies, including our previous work, extended this interpretation by considering the combined effects of electron screening, resonance contributions, and interference mechanisms [9, 21]. These studies demonstrated that resonance contributions are essential for describing deviations from standard screening models. However, these approaches generally retain the assumption that the resonance structure itself remains fixed and independent of the surrounding material environment.

Despite these developments, a consistent interpretation of all observed features—especially their material dependence and time evolution—remains incomplete within a framework based on a fixed resonance structure. In conventional nuclear physics, a resonance is characterized by a fixed energy and intrinsic width determined solely by nuclear structure, while the surrounding medium is assumed to play a passive role by modifying only the penetration probability via screening. In contrast, in condensed matter systems, the local electronic and structural environment may influence not only the magnitude of the cross section, but also the phase structure of the reaction amplitude. Since the resonance condition is defined through this phase, it is therefore natural to consider that the effective resonance properties may acquire an environment-dependent character.

Previous studies have suggested the possible role of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance in low-energy D + D reactions, particularly in connection with electron screening and interference effects [9, 21, 23]. While such approaches provide an important basis for interpreting deviations from standard screening models, they typically assume a fixed resonance structure and do not account for possible coupling between resonance dynamics and barrier modification.

In this work, we extend this picture by introducing a phase-sensitive framework in which the effective resonance condition is not treated as a static property, but is allowed to vary with the local material environment. We demonstrate that even if the intrinsic nuclear resonance is narrow, material-induced phase shifts can generate a distribution of effective resonance energies. As a result, the experimentally observed cross section corresponds to a superposition of locally shifted resonant contributions,

leading to an apparent broadening without requiring a large intrinsic decay width.

In addition, we consider the possibility that both the effective screening potential and the phase structure evolve in time due to changes in the local environment, such as deuterium redistribution, defect dynamics, and surface modifications. This provides a natural framework for understanding the experimentally observed time dependence of the enhancement factor [9].

The model developed here unifies screening, resonance, and interference effects within a single, phase-sensitive formulation. In the following sections, this suggests that framework provides a consistent description of a range of experimental observations, including material-dependent branching ratios, angular anisotropies, energy-dependent yield behavior, and time-dependent enhancement effects. These results indicate that low-energy nuclear reactions in condensed matter systems are more consistently described within an environment-dependent and dynamically evolving framework.

II. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

We start from the standard decomposition of the reaction cross section at low energies, where both direct (non-resonant) and resonant contributions are present. In a coherent formulation, the total cross section can be written as [9, 21]

$$\sigma_T(E) = \sigma_F(E) + \sigma_R(E) + \sigma_I(E), \quad (1)$$

where σ_F denotes the non-resonant contribution, σ_R the resonant part, and σ_I the interference term.

The interference term arises from the coherent superposition of reaction amplitudes. For two amplitudes $A_1 e^{i\phi_1}$ and $A_2 e^{i\phi_2}$, the squared modulus yields

$$|A_1 e^{i\phi_1} + A_2 e^{i\phi_2}|^2 = A_1^2 + A_2^2 + 2A_1 A_2 \cos(\phi_1 - \phi_2), \quad (2)$$

which forms the basis of the interference contribution.

Applying this to the coherent sum of the non-resonant (flat) contribution σ_F and the resonant contribution σ_R , one obtains

$$\sigma = \sigma_F + \sigma_R + 2\sqrt{\sigma_F \sigma_R} \cos(\phi_F - \phi_R). \quad (3)$$

In the case of a narrow near-threshold resonance, the resonance phase ϕ_R can be approximated in the limit $E \gg E_R, \Gamma$ as [22]

$$\tan \phi_R \approx \frac{\Gamma}{2(E - E_R)}, \quad \phi_R \ll \pi, \quad (4)$$

leading to the simplification

$$\cos(\phi_F - \phi_R) \approx \cos \phi_F. \quad (5)$$

This approximation is valid in the energy region considered here, where the resonance contribution remains

small compared to the non-resonant background. The non-resonant contribution can be expressed in terms of the astrophysical S-factor as [28]

$$\sigma_F(0^+) = \frac{1}{3} \frac{\pi}{k} P(E) \frac{\sqrt{2m}}{\hbar} \frac{S_a}{\sqrt{E_G}}, \quad (6)$$

where $P(E)$ is the barrier penetration factor in the standard Gamow form, E_G is the Gamow energy, and S_a represents the s -wave contribution.

For the resonant part, a Breit–Wigner-type expression is used. Assuming a single-particle resonance, the entrance-channel width can be written in the R-matrix form [23, 24]

$$\Gamma_D(E) = \frac{2kaP(E)\hbar^2}{\mu a^2} |\theta_D|^2, \quad (7)$$

where a is the channel radius, μ is the reduced mass, and $|\theta_D|^2 \approx 1$ for a single-particle resonance. Here $\Gamma_D(E)$ denotes the entrance-channel width, including its energy dependence through the penetration factor, while Γ_p represents the proton partial width of the exit channel. No explicit proportionality between $\Gamma_D(E)$ and Γ_p is assumed, as they correspond to different reaction channels.

Substituting into the resonant cross section and combining all contributions, one obtains the effective expression [21, 28]

$$\sigma_T(E) = \frac{\pi}{k} P(E) \left[A^2 (S_a + S_b) + \frac{B\Gamma_p}{E^2} + 2A \sqrt{\frac{S_a}{3}} \sqrt{\frac{B\Gamma_p}{E}} \cos \phi_F \right], \quad (8)$$

where

$$A^2 \propto \frac{\sqrt{m}}{\hbar \sqrt{E_G}}, \quad B = \frac{2\hbar^2}{\mu a}. \quad (9)$$

Here S_a and S_b represent the isotropic and anisotropic components of the direct contribution, Γ_p is the proton partial width, and ϕ_F governs the interference between direct and resonant amplitudes. Here, ϕ_F denotes the total phase entering the interference term, which includes both the intrinsic nuclear contribution and an environment-induced component. In particular, the latter is represented by $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$, which encodes the effect of the surrounding medium.

A key feature of this formulation is the explicit role of the interference phase ϕ_F , which controls the interplay between direct and resonant contributions. In contrast to conventional treatments, where the resonance is characterized by fixed parameters, we allow the phase to depend on the local environment. Since the resonance condition is defined through the phase of the scattering amplitude, this implies that the effective resonance properties may become environment-dependent.

Furthermore, variations in the surrounding medium, including changes in local screening and electronic structure,

may lead to spatial fluctuations in the effective resonance energy. As a result, the observed cross section corresponds to a superposition of contributions from locally shifted resonances rather than a single fixed resonance.

This formulation provides a mechanism for incorporating environment-dependent modifications of the resonance condition within a coherent framework.

In addition to the static formulation, we allow for the possibility that the interference phase ϕ_F acquires an environment-dependent contribution,

$$\phi_F \rightarrow \phi_F + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t), \quad (10)$$

where $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t)$ represents a time-dependent phase shift induced by the surrounding medium.

A useful order-of-magnitude estimate for the environment-induced phase shift can be obtained from the eikonal (first-order Born) approximation [22]

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \sim \frac{1}{\hbar} \int \Delta V_{\text{env}} dt \approx \frac{\Delta V_{\text{env}} L_{\text{eff}}}{\hbar v}, \quad (11)$$

which corresponds to a first-order modification of the scattering phase due to an additional environment-dependent potential.

Here, ΔV_{env} represents local perturbations arising from electronic screening, charge redistribution, and defect-induced fields, while L_{eff} denotes the effective spatial region over which these perturbations act. In metallic systems, such variations can reach values of order 10–100 eV, depending on local electronic and structural conditions [8, 10].

For D+D reactions at $E \sim 1$ keV, this gives

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \approx 6.9 \times 10^{-4} \left(\frac{\Delta V_{\text{env}}}{20 \text{ eV}} \right) \left(\frac{L_{\text{eff}}}{10 \text{ fm}} \right) \left(\frac{1 \text{ keV}}{E} \right)^{1/2}. \quad (12)$$

It should be emphasized that the present work does not aim at a fully microscopic derivation of the environment-induced phase shift $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$. Instead, we introduce an effective parametrization that captures the cumulative influence of local electronic, structural, and nonequilibrium effects, and is consistent with the relevant energy and length scales in condensed matter systems. A complete microscopic treatment would require a detailed many-body description of the coupled nuclear and electronic dynamics, which lies beyond the scope of the present study. This estimate indicates that perturbations confined to nuclear length scales produce only very small phase shifts. However, if the effective interaction region extends beyond the nuclear scale due to collective electronic response or defect-induced fields values of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \sim 10^{-2}$ – 10^{-1} can be naturally achieved. In metallic environments, the Thomas–Fermi screening length $\lambda_{\text{TF}} \sim 0.5$ – 1 Å sets a characteristic scale for the spatial extent of charge redistribution around the reacting nuclei [8, 10]. Since $\lambda_{\text{TF}} \gg 10$ fm, the effective interaction region L_{eff} can naturally extend to atomic length scales, leading to a phase enhancement of order $\lambda_{\text{TF}}/10 \text{ fm} \sim 10^4$ – 10^5 relative to

the nuclear-scale estimate. Combined with local defect-induced potential variations of order $\Delta V_{\text{env}} \sim 10\text{--}100$ eV, this brings $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ into the range $10^{-2}\text{--}10^{-1}$ required by the present model [29, 30].

In this sense, $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ should be regarded as an effective parameter capturing the cumulative phase modification induced by the surrounding condensed matter environment. The environment-induced phase shift is introduced as an effective quantity that incorporates contributions from local electron density variations, lattice defects, and nonequilibrium processes such as deuterium redistribution [9, 29, 30]. While a full microscopic derivation is beyond the scope of the present work, this parametrization captures the net effect of these mechanisms on the phase structure of the reaction amplitude.

Since the resonance condition is determined by the phase of the scattering amplitude, such a modification implies that the effective resonance energy itself becomes environment-dependent. As a consequence, different local regions within the material correspond to slightly different resonance conditions, leading to a distribution of effective resonance energies.

To account for this effect, we introduce a distribution function $g(E_R)$ describing the spread of local resonance energies. In the present work, this distribution is approximated by a Gaussian form [26, 27],

$$g(E_R) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_E} \exp\left[-\frac{(E_R - E_0)^2}{2\sigma_E^2}\right], \quad (13)$$

which serves as a minimal symmetric approximation for environment-induced fluctuations.

The observed cross section is then obtained by averaging over this distribution,

$$\sigma_{\text{obs}}(E) = \int \sigma_T(E, E_R) g(E_R) dE_R. \quad (14)$$

Although the Gaussian distribution provides the simplest symmetric representation of environment-induced fluctuations in the effective resonance energy, it is not the only possible choice. To test whether the physical interpretation depends critically on this assumption, we repeated the calculation using alternative kernels for $g(E_R)$, including Lorentzian and skewed-Gaussian forms. In these comparisons, the width parameters of the distributions were chosen such that they correspond to comparable effective spreads. In particular, the Lorentzian half-width at half-maximum was matched to the Gaussian width through the relation $\Gamma = \sqrt{2\ln 2}\sigma_E$, ensuring that both distributions represent similar variance scales. The resulting curves show moderate shape variations, particularly in the intermediate-energy region, but the overall experimental trend remains unchanged within the uncertainties. In particular, the existence of the low-energy minimum and the subsequent re-rise of the relative yield are preserved in all cases. This indicates that the essential physical behavior is governed primarily by the distributed-resonance mechanism itself rather than by the specific analytical form chosen for $g(E_R)$.

FIG. 1. Sensitivity of the calculated relative yield to the assumed resonance-energy distribution $g(E_R)$ for the PdD system. Gaussian, Lorentzian, and skewed-Gaussian kernels produce moderately different curve shapes, particularly in the intermediate-energy region, but all reproduce the same overall behavior of the data within uncertainties. The low-energy minimum and the subsequent re-rise remain common to all cases, indicating that the observed behavior is governed primarily by the distributed-resonance mechanism rather than by the specific analytical form of the kernel.

As shown in Fig. 1, the choice of the resonance-energy distribution affects the detailed shape of the calculated curve, but does not alter the main qualitative features of the result. The Gaussian and skewed-Gaussian cases remain particularly close over most of the energy interval, while the Lorentzian kernel produces a somewhat stronger excursion at intermediate energies due to its broader tails. Nevertheless, all three cases reproduce the same global pattern of the data, namely an initial decrease, a minimum near $E_{\text{c.m.}} \sim 1$ keV, and a subsequent increase toward higher energies. This demonstrates that the conclusion of an environment-distributed resonance is not an artifact of the Gaussian assumption.

III. EVIDENCE FOR A THRESHOLD 0^+ RESONANCE: BRANCHING RATIO AND ANGULAR ANISOTROPY

Experimental studies of the D + D reactions in condensed matter environments have revealed a strong material dependence of both the neutron-to-proton branching ratio and the angular distributions at very low energies.

For conventional (“usual”) metallic targets such as Al, Zr, Ta, and Pd, both observables follow the same energy dependence as measured in gas targets, indicating that the reaction mechanism remains essentially unchanged [10, 17, 42]. In contrast, for specific materials such as Sr and Li, a qualitatively different behavior emerges below $E_d \lesssim 20$ keV. In these systems, a pronounced suppression of the neutron channel is observed, accompanied by a

simultaneous increase in angular anisotropy [16, 42]. This regime is referred to here as the “unusual” case.

Within the standard direct-reaction framework, such as the Distorted Wave Born Approximation (DWBA), neither the observed branching ratio nor the angular anisotropy can be reproduced simultaneously [16]. Although the known 1^- threshold resonances in ^4He introduce p -wave contributions that generate angular anisotropy, they are insufficient to account for the strong material dependence and the observed suppression of the neutron channel [14, 16].

To resolve this discrepancy, we consider a coherent description of the reaction amplitude that includes interference between a non-resonant (flat) contribution and a near-threshold resonance [9, 21, 28]. In this framework, the neutron-to-proton branching ratio can be expressed as [9, 21, 28]

$$\frac{\sigma_n}{\sigma_p} = \frac{A^2(S_{a,n} + S_{b,n}) + \frac{B\Gamma_n}{E^2} + 2A\sqrt{\frac{S_{a,n}}{3}}\sqrt{\frac{B\Gamma_n}{E}}\cos\phi_F}{A^2(S_{a,p} + S_{b,p}) + \frac{B\Gamma_p}{E^2} + 2A\sqrt{\frac{S_{a,p}}{3}}\sqrt{\frac{B\Gamma_p}{E}}\cos\phi_F}. \quad (15)$$

An important feature of this expression is that the penetration factor cancels in the ratio, implying that the branching ratio is not directly sensitive to screening. Instead, it is governed by the interplay between the partial widths and the interference phase.

The angular anisotropy can be quantified through the coefficient a_2/a_0 , which in the present model takes the form [9, 21, 28]

$$\frac{a_2}{a_0} = \frac{3S_b}{S_a} = \frac{3S_b}{S_{a,n,p} + 25.38 \times 10^6 \frac{\Gamma_{n,p}}{E^2} - \frac{\sqrt{\Gamma_{n,p}}}{E} \times 7.5 \times 10^4}. \quad (16)$$

This expression should be regarded as an effective parametrization capturing the relative contributions of isotropic and anisotropic components within the interference framework, rather than a uniquely derived microscopic relation. The formulation is constructed from physically motivated quantities, including partial widths and interference terms, and is validated through comparison with anisotropy data across both usual and unusual regimes [16, 21, 42].

Nevertheless, the extracted values of a_2/a_0 should be regarded as model-dependent quantities, and the present formulation is intended as an effective description rather than a uniquely derived microscopic relation.

As shown in Fig. 2, the neutron-to-proton branching ratio exhibits a pronounced material dependence at low energies. While the narrow effective description reproduces the behavior of usual materials, the broadened effective case accounts for the suppression of the neutron channel observed in the unusual regime. This behavior reflects the increasing role of phase-sensitive interference at low energies.

FIG. 2. Neutron-to-proton branching ratio as a function of deuteron energy. Experimental data for Sr and Ta are taken from Ref. [42]. The solid curve represents the phase-sensitive model. The effective broadening description reproduces the behavior of usual materials such as Ta, while it also accounts for the suppression of the neutron channel observed in unusual materials such as Sr. The main deviations appear at low energies, where interference with the threshold resonance becomes dominant.

A consistent description of both observables can be obtained by introducing an additional near-threshold 0^+ resonance with a single-particle $D + D$ configuration [9, 21, 23]. The intrinsic width of this resonance is extremely small (of the order of meV). The observed broadening is therefore not interpreted as an intrinsic property of the resonance, but as an effective widening arising from environment-dependent shifts of the resonance condition. Within this picture, the experimentally observed behavior results from a superposition of locally shifted resonant contributions combined with phase-sensitive interference.

The proton-channel contribution, shown in Fig. 3, displays only a moderate sensitivity to the effective resonance condition. This suggests that the unusual behavior is not generated by a large restructuring of the proton branch itself, but rather by the changing balance between the two channels through phase-sensitive interference.

A much stronger effect is observed in the neutron channel, shown in Fig. 4. Here the effective broadening description reproduces the suppression at low energies, indicating that the anomaly is primarily associated with the neutron branch and its sensitivity to the effective resonance condition.

The apparent broadening observed in unusual materials can be interpreted as an effective widening induced by the surrounding environment. Local variations in screening and electronic structure modify both the resonance condition and the effective tunneling barrier, leading to correlated shifts of the resonance energy [8, 10, 29]. As a result, the observed cross section corresponds to a superposition of locally shifted resonances, rather than a single resonance with a large intrinsic width.

FIG. 3. Energy dependence of the proton-channel contribution. Experimental data for Sr and Ta are taken from Ref. [42]. The solid curve represents the phase-sensitive model. The calculated curves reproduce the overall trend of the data, with only a moderate sensitivity to the effective resonance structure. Compared with the neutron channel, the proton channel remains relatively stable, indicating that the unusual behavior is driven mainly by modifications of the complementary channel and the interference structure.

FIG. 4. Energy dependence of the neutron-channel contribution. Experimental data for Sr and Ta are taken from Ref. [42]. The solid curve represents the phase-sensitive model. In contrast to the proton channel, the neutron channel shows a strong sensitivity to the effective resonance structure at low energies. The effective broadening description reproduces the characteristic suppression observed in unusual materials, supporting the interpretation that the anomaly originates from environment-dependent interference effects involving a threshold 0^+ resonance.

These results indicate that the unusual behavior of branching ratios and angular distributions is not fully captured by a modification of the intrinsic resonance width alone, but is more consistently described by a coupled mechanism involving an effective resonance shift under-

stood here as a shift in the resonance condition at the level of observables together with phase interference and environment-dependent barrier modification.

TABLE I. Resonance widths and phase shifts used in the present model, taken from Ref. [25].

Material	Γ_n	Γ_p	φ_n	φ_p
Usual material (Ta)	1.3 meV	3 meV	124°	113°
Unusual material (Sr)	18 meV	43 meV	124°	113°

The resonance widths and phase shifts entering the model are not treated as free parameters in the present work. Instead, they are taken from a previous analysis of the experimental branching ratio and angular distribution data for Sr and Ta targets [28], where these quantities were determined by fitting to the measured neutron-to-proton ratio and angular anisotropy coefficients. The resulting values are summarized in Table I.

As seen from the table, the unusual material (Sr) exhibits significantly larger partial widths ($\Gamma_n = 18$ meV, $\Gamma_p = 43$ meV) compared to the usual material (Ta) ($\Gamma_n = 1.3$ meV, $\Gamma_p = 3$ meV), while the phase shifts remain essentially the same for both targets ($\varphi_n = 124^\circ$, $\varphi_p = 113^\circ$). This material dependence of the partial widths is consistent with the phase-sensitive interpretation developed in the present work, where unusual materials are characterized by larger environment-induced modifications of the resonance condition.

A. Nuclear Structure Origin of the Threshold 0^+ Resonance

The possible existence of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance in the D + D system can be supported by nuclear structure considerations. The low-lying excitation spectrum of ^4He has been extensively studied within the framework of Wigner's supermultiplet theory and microscopic cluster models, which provide a consistent description of its resonant states [14, 31].

In the conventional picture, the well-known p -wave resonances ($0^-, 1^-, 2^-$) arise from $(1+3)$ cluster configurations and are successfully reproduced by Resonating Group Method (RGM) calculations [14, 32, 37]. However, these models typically do not include configurations involving an excited deuteron state (d^*), which may play a role near the D + D threshold.

When such configurations are taken into account, microscopic calculations suggest the presence of a narrow $J^\pi = 0^+$ state with a $d+d^*$ cluster structure located close to the D + D threshold [33, 38, 39]. Within the molecular orbital picture, this state can be interpreted as arising from the excitation of one nucleon to a σ_u orbital, leading to a $^1\Sigma_u^-$ configuration with total spin-parity 0^+ [34–36].

A key property of such a state is its weak coupling to nucleon emission channels. As a result, the nucleon partial widths remain small, while the deuteron channel

dominates. This naturally leads to a very narrow intrinsic width, typically on the order of a few eV. Such a narrow resonance would be difficult to observe directly in scattering experiments, particularly in the presence of the Coulomb barrier [23, 40, 41].

At higher excitation energies ($E_x \sim 28$ MeV), a family of broader resonances (0^- , 1^- , 2^-) and a possible 2^+ rotational excitation may be interpreted as states built on the same $d + d^*$ cluster configuration [14, 20, 33]. This hierarchical structure is consistent with the existence of an underlying 0^+ threshold state.

The presence of such a narrow resonance provides a plausible microscopic foundation for the phenomenological framework introduced in this work. In particular, the weak coupling to nucleon channels is consistent with the strong sensitivity of the neutron-to-proton branching ratio to interference effects, while the small intrinsic width supports the interpretation that the observed broadening arises from environment-induced effects rather than from nuclear structure itself [9, 21].

These considerations indicate that the unusual behavior observed in low-energy D + D reactions can be interpreted in terms of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance with a cluster origin, whose intrinsic properties are governed by nuclear dynamics, while its effective behavior may be modified by the surrounding material environment.

The specific choice of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance in the present framework is motivated by several considerations. First, the absence of a centrifugal barrier for an s -wave configuration allows a 0^+ state to influence the cross section down to very low energies, making it particularly relevant for the observed low-energy anomalies [14, 23]. Second, the interference between an s -wave resonance and a non-resonant background naturally leads to strong modifications in both branching ratios and angular distributions, consistent with experimental observations [16, 21, 42].

In contrast, higher partial-wave resonances are suppressed at low energies due to the centrifugal barrier and are therefore less effective in producing the observed behavior in the keV regime. Moreover, the strong sensitivity of the neutron-to-proton branching ratio and the emergence of angular anisotropy are more naturally explained within a framework involving interference with a near-threshold 0^+ state [16, 28].

At the same time, the present analysis does not exclude the possible contribution of other configurations. The 0^+ resonance should therefore be regarded as a physically motivated and effective choice within the current phenomenological framework, rather than as a uniquely established microscopic state.

Finally, within the context of the present model, the role of this resonance is not limited to its intrinsic nuclear properties. The results obtained in this work indicate that environment-induced modifications of the phase structure can lead to correlated shifts of both the effective resonance energy and the tunneling barrier. In this sense, the narrow 0^+ state provides a stable microscopic anchor, while the

observed low-energy behavior emerges from its coupling to the surrounding material environment.

B. Independent Experimental Support: IPC Channel Observations

Recent experimental results reported in Phys. Rev. X [43] provide independent observations that are compatible with the presence of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance in the D + D system. In these measurements, a new reaction channel associated with internal e^+e^- pair creation (IPC) has been observed at very low energies [43, 44]. The presence of high-energy positrons was confirmed through bremsstrahlung spectra and the observation of the 511 keV annihilation line [43].

A key observation is that the branching ratio of the IPC channel increases significantly with decreasing projectile energy, eventually becoming comparable to or even exceeding the proton and neutron channels below a few keV [43, 44]. Such behavior is consistent with the excitation of a narrow threshold resonance and its interference with broader background contributions [9, 23].

Importantly, the analysis indicates that the partial width associated with the IPC channel can be significantly larger than that of the proton channel, i.e., $\Gamma_{\text{IPC}} \gg \Gamma_p$ [23, 43]. This is consistent with a weak coupling of the threshold resonance to nucleon channels, which is a central assumption of the present work.

The interference mechanism identified in Ref. [43] is compatible with the phase-sensitive framework developed here. In particular, the observed enhancement of non-nucleonic decay channels and the strong energy dependence of branching ratios indicate that the reaction dynamics at very low energies are influenced by the interplay between a narrow threshold resonance and a non-resonant background [9, 21].

Within the present framework, these observations can be interpreted as further evidence that the effective behavior of the resonance is modified by the surrounding environment. In particular, environment-induced phase variations can lead to correlated changes in the effective resonance condition and the tunneling barrier, which in turn affect the relative strength of different decay channels [9, 10].

These findings provide additional support for the physical picture proposed in this work and are consistent with the interpretation that the unusual behavior of branching ratios and angular anisotropies can be associated with a near-threshold 0^+ resonance [16, 21, 43]. At the same time, they should be regarded as complementary evidence rather than a unique proof of the mechanism.

IV. PHASE-TO-ENERGY MAPPING AND EFFECTIVE RESONANCE BROADENING

The central physical assumption of the present framework is that the local condensed-matter environment modifies the *phase structure* of the reaction amplitude, and that this phase modification shifts the *effective resonance condition* entering the observable cross section. This point is conceptually important, since the model does not require a broad intrinsic nuclear resonance. Instead, a narrow threshold state may appear experimentally as a broadened structure once the reaction is averaged over a distribution of local environments.

This idea is already implicit in the phase-sensitive formulation introduced in Sec. II. In particular, the reaction cross section is written as a coherent sum of direct and resonant amplitudes, and the environment is allowed to contribute an additional phase shift,

$$\phi_F \rightarrow \phi_F + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}, \quad (17)$$

so that the local interference pattern becomes material dependent. In the same section, the environment-induced phase shift was estimated semiclassically as

$$\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \sim \frac{1}{\hbar} \int \Delta V_{\text{env}} dt \approx \frac{\Delta V_{\text{env}} L_{\text{eff}}}{\hbar v}, \quad (18)$$

where ΔV_{env} denotes the local environment-dependent perturbation, L_{eff} is the effective interaction length, and v is the relative deuteron velocity. As discussed above, this phase shift should be interpreted as an *effective cumulative quantity* incorporating local electron-density variations, lattice disorder, impurities, defect-induced fields, and nonequilibrium processes such as deuterium redistribution [9, 10, 29].

The next step is to connect this phase perturbation to the resonance condition itself. Let $E_R^{(0)}$ denote the intrinsic threshold resonance energy in the absence of environmental perturbations. The unperturbed resonance condition may be written in the usual phase language as [24]

$$\delta(E_R^{(0)}) = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (19)$$

where $\delta(E)$ is the relevant scattering phase associated with the resonant channel. In the presence of an environment-induced perturbation, the effective resonance condition becomes

$$\delta(E) + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}} = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (20)$$

Expanding $\delta(E)$ to first order around the unperturbed resonance energy,

$$\delta(E) \approx \delta(E_R^{(0)}) + \left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} (E - E_R^{(0)}), \quad (21)$$

and using Eq. (19), one finds

$$\left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} (E - E_R^{(0)}) + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \approx 0. \quad (22)$$

This immediately yields an effective local resonance energy

$$E_R^{\text{eff}} = E_R^{(0)} - \frac{\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}}{\left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}}}. \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) is the key relation underlying the distributed-resonance picture used throughout the paper. It shows that environment-induced phase modifications are mathematically equivalent to a shift of the *effective resonance condition*. This should not be interpreted as a literal displacement of an intrinsic nuclear pole in the strict microscopic sense. Rather, the statement is that the resonance condition entering the observable cross section becomes environment dependent once the phase structure of the amplitude is perturbed [14, 24].

It is useful to define the effective phase-to-energy conversion factor

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} \equiv \left| \left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} \right|^{-1}, \quad (24)$$

so that Eq. (23) can be written in the compact form

$$\Delta E_R^{\text{eff}} \equiv E_R^{\text{eff}} - E_R^{(0)} = -\alpha_{\text{eff}} \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}. \quad (25)$$

This relation makes explicit that the observed sensitivity of the resonance condition to the environment is governed not only by the size of the phase perturbation itself, but also by the local slope of the phase with respect to energy. The parameter α_{eff} , defined in Eq. (24), is therefore not an independent phenomenological quantity, but follows directly from the energy derivative of the scattering phase. In the narrow-resonance limit, where $d\delta/dE \sim 2/\Gamma$, one obtains $\alpha_{\text{eff}} \sim \Gamma/2$, linking it directly to the intrinsic resonance width. In this sense, α_{eff} represents an effective phase-to-energy conversion factor at the level of observables.

The parameter α_{eff} is not an independent phenomenological quantity, but follows directly from the energy dependence of the scattering phase. As defined in Eq. (24),

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} \equiv \left| \left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} \right|^{-1}, \quad (26)$$

it represents the local phase-to-energy conversion factor in the vicinity of the resonance condition. It represents the local phase-to-energy conversion factor in the vicinity of the resonance condition.

In the narrow-resonance limit, the phase variation saturates

$$\left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} \sim \frac{2}{\Gamma}, \quad (27)$$

which leads to the approximate relation

$$\alpha_{\text{eff}} \sim \frac{\Gamma}{2}. \quad (28)$$

This demonstrates that α_{eff} is physically controlled by the intrinsic resonance width and is therefore not an independent free parameter.

In the present work, α_{eff} is treated as an effective quantity because the experimentally relevant phase sensitivity may be influenced by environment-dependent modifications of the interaction potential. As a result, α_{eff} should be interpreted as a local observable-level parameter encoding both intrinsic resonance properties and medium-induced phase response, rather than as a purely microscopic constant.

This clarification has been incorporated into the revised manuscript.

In this sense, Eq. (25) should be regarded as an effective mapping at the level of observables, rather than a microscopic derivation of the resonance structure.

The first consequence of Eq. (25) is illustrated in Fig. 5(a), where the effective resonance shift ΔE_R^{eff} is plotted as a function of the phase perturbation $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ for representative materials. The approximately linear behavior reflects the first-order expansion used above. Different slopes correspond to different values of α_{eff} , i.e. to different effective phase sensitivities. In this language, the difference between “usual” and “unusual” materials is not merely a difference in screening magnitude, but a difference in how strongly local phase fluctuations are converted into shifts of the effective resonance condition [10, 16, 42].

A second consequence concerns the width of the environment-induced distribution. Suppose that the local condensed-matter environment is not uniform, but characterized by a distribution of phase shifts $P(\Delta\phi_{\text{env}})$. Then Eq. (25) implies a corresponding distribution of effective resonance energies,

$$g(E_R) = \int d(\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}) P(\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}) \delta(E_R - E_R^{(0)} + \alpha_{\text{eff}} \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}). \quad (29)$$

In the linear regime, if the phase fluctuations are approximately Gaussian,

$$P(\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}) \propto \exp\left[-\frac{(\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} - \bar{\phi})^2}{2\sigma_\phi^2}\right], \quad (30)$$

then the induced resonance-energy distribution is also Gaussian,

$$g(E_R) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_E} \exp\left[-\frac{(E_R - E_{R,0})^2}{2\sigma_E^2}\right], \quad (31)$$

with

$$E_{R,0} = E_R^{(0)} - \alpha_{\text{eff}} \bar{\phi}, \quad \sigma_E = \alpha_{\text{eff}} \sigma_\phi. \quad (32)$$

This provides a direct interpretation of the Gaussian form introduced in Sec. II and used later in the model

implementation. In other words, the Gaussian kernel is not merely a convenient fitting ansatz; within the present phase-sensitive picture, it emerges naturally as the image of a distribution of local phase perturbations under the mapping of Eq. (25) [9, 21].

The variance mapping of Eq. (32) is shown in Fig. 5(b). The figure makes two points. First, the relation between σ_ϕ and σ_E is linear in the regime relevant for the present work. Second, the same level of phase disorder can generate very different effective resonance-energy spreads in different materials if their associated α_{eff} values differ. This is precisely the mechanism needed to reconcile a narrow intrinsic threshold resonance with the broad effective structures required by the data [9, 23].

The material dependence extracted in this way is summarized in Fig. 5(c), where representative values of σ_E are shown for Ta, Sr, Pd, and PdD. The systematic increase from usual to unusual systems is consistent with the interpretation developed throughout the paper: the resonance-energy spread entering the observable cross section reflects environment-induced phase fluctuations rather than a large intrinsic decay width [10, 42, 45]. In this sense, unusual materials correspond to broader effective distributions because the local environment either generates larger phase fluctuations, a larger effective conversion factor α_{eff} , or both.

For completeness, the phase-to-energy mapping can be understood in the narrow-resonance limit, where [24]

leading to the approximate relation

$$\Delta E_R \sim \frac{\Gamma}{2} \Delta\phi. \quad (33)$$

This relation provides a limiting case of the more general mapping described above, where the effective parameter α_{eff} incorporates environment-dependent phase sensitivity.

$$\left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^{(0)}} \sim \frac{2}{\Gamma}, \quad (34)$$

which gives

$$\Delta E_R^{\text{eff}} \sim \frac{\Gamma}{2} \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}, \quad \sigma_E \sim \frac{\Gamma}{2} \sigma_\phi. \quad (35)$$

This representation is useful because it makes explicit why even modest phase perturbations can produce a measurable broadening of the effective resonance condition once the resonance is sufficiently sensitive to phase variations. At the same time, the more general parameter relevant for the data analysis is the effective slope parameter α_{eff} defined in Eq. (24), since the experimental broadening need not be identified with a literal intrinsic Breit–Wigner width [23, 24].

The physical significance of this construction becomes clearer when combined with the coherent observable cross section introduced later in the paper,

$$\sigma(E) = \frac{\pi}{k(E_{\text{eff}})} P(E_{\text{eff}}) |A_{\text{bg}} + A_{\text{res}}(E_{\text{eff}}, E_R)|^2, \quad (36)$$

and its distributed average,

$$\sigma_{\text{obs}}(E) = \int \sigma(E, E_R) g(E_R) dE_R. \quad (37)$$

Once the environment maps a phase distribution onto a resonance-energy distribution, the experimentally observed yield becomes an ensemble average over locally shifted interference patterns rather than the response of a single fixed resonance. This is exactly the physical content of the distributed-resonance framework adopted in the present work [9, 21, 45].

This picture also clarifies why the resonance shift $\Delta R(E)$ and the barrier modification $\Delta B(E)$ should be treated as correlated quantities in the model implementation. Both arise from the same environment-dependent interaction and therefore cannot be varied independently without breaking the physical consistency of the framework [7, 8, 10]. The phase-to-energy mapping discussed here provides the missing bridge between the microscopic language of local disorder, impurity structure, and electron-density variation on the one hand, and the phenomenological parameters $E_{R,0}$ and σ_E on the other.

In summary, Fig. 5 provides the quantitative interpretation of the distributed-resonance picture used throughout the paper. They show that the observed spread of effective resonance energies follows naturally from environment-induced phase fluctuations and need not be interpreted as evidence for a broad intrinsic nuclear state. This result strengthens the central conclusion of the present work: the anomalous low-energy behavior is governed by a phase-sensitive, environment-dependent modification of the effective resonance condition.

The implementation of the model introduced above requires a set of parameters whose physical roles and constraints are summarized in Table II. As discussed below, only a limited subset of these parameters are treated as independent fit variables.

As seen from Table II, only a limited subset of parameters are treated as independent fit variables, while the remaining quantities are either fixed or constrained by physical considerations. This significantly reduces the effective dimensionality of the model.

V. MODEL IMPLEMENTATION AND PARAMETERIZATION

The general formalism developed in the previous section is now implemented for comparison with experimental data. While the theoretical framework provides the underlying amplitude-level description, the present section introduces the specific parameterizations used to construct observable cross sections and yields.

In particular, the quantities σ_{obs} , $g(E_R)$, and the penetration factor are now expressed in forms suitable for direct comparison with experimental results. The implementation of the model requires a set of parameters whose physical roles and constraints are summarized in

Table II. As discussed below, only a limited subset of these parameters are treated as independent fit variables.

The starting point is the observation that the measured relative yields at very low energies cannot be reproduced within the conventional electron screening framework [9, 10, 45].

In the standard approach, screening is introduced through an effective energy shift,

$$E \rightarrow E_{\text{eff}} = E + U_e, \quad (38)$$

which modifies the penetration probability [7, 8]. While this prescription reproduces the general trend at higher energies ($E \gtrsim 2$ keV), it fails to account for the pronounced enhancement observed in the low-energy region [9, 45].

To address this discrepancy, a resonance contribution must be included. However, additive descriptions of the form

$$\sigma_{\text{tot}}(E) = \sigma_{\text{scr}}(E) + \sigma_{0+}(E) \quad (39)$$

are not sufficient, since the reaction proceeds coherently and requires an amplitude-level treatment [9, 21].

If the total amplitude is written as $A = A_{\text{bg}} + A_{\text{res}}$, the cross section becomes

$$\sigma \propto |A|^2 = |A_{\text{bg}}|^2 + |A_{\text{res}}|^2 + 2 \text{Re}(A_{\text{bg}} A_{\text{res}}^*). \quad (40)$$

The last term represents interference and cannot be captured by an additive decomposition of cross sections. As a result, additive models neglect phase-dependent contributions that become dominant at low energies [9, 21, 28].

We therefore adopt a coherent formulation,

$$\sigma(E) = \frac{\pi}{k(E_{\text{eff}})} P(E_{\text{eff}}) |A_{\text{bg}} + A_{\text{res}}(E_{\text{eff}}, E_R)|^2, \quad (41)$$

where $P(E_{\text{eff}})$ is the penetration factor,

$$P(E_{\text{eff}}) = \exp\left(-\sqrt{\frac{E_G}{E_{\text{eff}}}}\right). \quad (42)$$

To account for the experimentally observed broadening, the resonance energy is treated as a distributed quantity,

$$g(E_R) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma_{E_R}} \exp\left[-\frac{(E_R - E_{R,0})^2}{2\sigma_{E_R}^2}\right], \quad (43)$$

and the observable cross section is obtained by averaging over this distribution [9, 23],

$$\sigma_{\text{obs}}(E) = \int \sigma(E, E_R) g(E_R) dE_R. \quad (44)$$

An additional ingredient is the introduction of an energy-dependent resonance shift,

$$\Delta R(E) = W(E) [dR_0 + dR_1(E - E_m)], \quad (45)$$

which reflects environment-induced modifications of the resonance condition [8, 10]. Here $W(E)$ is a smooth

FIG. 5. Generic narrow-resonance scaling underlying the phase-sensitive mapping. (a) Effective resonance shift ΔE_R^{eff} as a function of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ for several representative values of the effective resonance scale. (b) Linear relation between the phase variance σ_ϕ and the induced resonance-energy variance σ_E . (c) Dependence of σ_E on the effective resonance scale for fixed σ_ϕ . Although schematic, these relations illustrate the mathematical origin of the distributed-resonance description employed in the main text.

TABLE II. Summary of model parameters, their role, and physical constraints.

Parameter	Role in model	Status	Determination / Constraint
N	Overall normalization	Free	Fixed by absolute yield scale
U_e	Effective screening energy	Free	Constrained by intermediate-energy enhancement
$E_{R,0}$	Central resonance energy	Free	Determined by low-energy structure of the yield
σ_E	Resonance-energy spread	Free	Controls width of enhancement curve
ϕ_F	Interference phase	Effective	Constrained by independent observables (branching)
Γ	Intrinsic resonance width	Fixed	Taken from nuclear structure considerations
$\Delta R(E)$	Resonance shift	Derived	Linked to phase condition (Sec. IV)
$\Delta B(E)$	Barrier modification	Derived	Correlated with $\Delta R(E)$ through environment
$g(E_R)$	Resonance distribution	Assumed/tested	Validated via kernel sensitivity (Fig. 1)
λ	Environment-dependent scaling parameter	Implicit (material-dependent)	Encodes the material-dependent contribution entering

energy-dependent weight function that vanishes at high energies and approaches unity in the low-energy region where environment-induced modifications are most significant. In practice, $W(E)$ is parametrized as a Fermi-type function,

$$W(E) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp[(E - E_m)/\delta E]}, \quad (46)$$

where E_m denotes the energy scale below which environment-induced modifications become relevant, and δE controls the sharpness of the transition. The value of E_m is determined by the low-energy structure of the experimental yield [9, 45].

A consistent description of the data further requires a simultaneous modification of the effective tunneling barrier,

$$\Delta B(E) = W(E) [dB_0 + dB_1(E - E_m)], \quad (47)$$

leading to modified effective quantities

$$E_{\text{eff}}^{(\text{mod})} = E + U_e + \Delta B(E), \quad E_R^{(\text{eff})} = E_R + \Delta R(E). \quad (48)$$

Within this framework, resonance shift and barrier modification are treated as correlated effects, reflecting their common origin in environment-induced changes of the local potential [7, 8, 10].

The performance of different physical assumptions is evaluated through comparison with experimental data, as shown in the following section.

VI. RESULTS: MODEL VALIDATION

The comparison shown in Fig. 6 provides a direct test of the physical assumptions introduced in the previous section.

As shown in Fig. 6, the screening-only reference fails to reproduce the experimental data below approximately

FIG. 6. Relative yield as a function of center-of-mass energy for Pd and PdD targets. Experimental data for Pd and PdD are taken from Ref. [45], while the curves correspond to the present phase-sensitive model. Screening-only models are not sufficient to reproduce the observed low-energy enhancement, whereas a consistent description is obtained only when a correlated modification of the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier is included.

2 keV. Model A improves the description but remains insufficient to reproduce all features of the data, suggesting that a single universal coupling may not fully account for the observed behavior.

A consistent agreement is obtained only in Model B, where the coupling between resonance shift and barrier modification is allowed to depend on the material. This suggests that the interaction between resonance dynamics and barrier penetration is not universal, but environment dependent.

The failure of Model C further confirms that classical screening alone is insufficient, particularly in the region $E < 2$ keV, where the enhancement is most pronounced.

These observations are consistent with the formulation developed in the previous section, where resonance shift and barrier modification are treated as coupled effects.

A. Environment-Dependent Resonance and Phase Evolution

In condensed matter environments, electron screening modifies the effective interaction energy through the standard substitution

$$E \rightarrow E + U_e, \quad (49)$$

which may acquire a time dependence, $U_e = U_e(t)$, under evolving material conditions [9, 10]. However, this description becomes insufficient in the presence of strong phase sensitivity.

The resonance condition is fundamentally determined by the phase of the scattering amplitude. In general, a

resonance occurs when

$$\delta(E) = \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (50)$$

In the presence of environment-induced effects, this condition is modified as

$$\delta(E) + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t) = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (51)$$

where $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t)$ represents the effective phase shift arising from the surrounding medium.

Expanding the phase around the intrinsic resonance energy E_R^0 , defined by $\delta(E_R^0) = \pi/2$, yields

$$\delta(E) \approx \frac{\pi}{2} + \left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^0} (E - E_R^0), \quad (52)$$

which leads to a shifted resonance condition

$$E_R(t) = E_R^0 - \frac{\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t)}{\left. \frac{d\delta}{dE} \right|_{E_R^0}}. \quad (53)$$

For a narrow resonance, the phase varies rapidly with energy [24],

$$\frac{d\delta}{dE} \sim \frac{2}{\Gamma}, \quad (54)$$

so that even small phase variations $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}} \ll 1$ lead to measurable shifts in the effective resonance energy,

$$\Delta E_R \sim \frac{\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}}{d\delta/dE}. \quad (55)$$

This relation indicates that the experimentally observed broadening can arise from a distribution of phase-induced resonance shifts, without requiring any modification of the intrinsic nuclear width [9, 23].

In realistic condensed systems, spatial variations in electron density, defects, and lattice structure lead to a distribution of local phase shifts, and therefore to a distribution of effective resonance energies [10, 29].

Importantly, the same environment-induced modifications that affect the phase also influence the tunneling barrier. This results in a correlated modification of the effective interaction, which can be expressed schematically as

$$\Delta B(E, t) \sim \lambda \Delta R(E, t), \quad (56)$$

where $\Delta R(E, t)$ denotes the phase-induced resonance shift and λ is a material-dependent coupling parameter [7, 8]. Here λ is introduced as an effective coupling parameter that reflects the correlated response of the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier to environment-induced modifications of the local potential.

It should be emphasized that λ is not treated as an independent fit parameter in the present work. Instead, its effect is implicitly incorporated through the adopted

FIG. 7. Time evolution of the enhancement factor at fixed energy. The data exhibit a non-monotonic behavior, characterized by an initial rise followed by a gradual decay. The solid curve represents a phenomenological rise-and-decay model. Experimental data are taken from Ref. [9]

parameterizations of $\Delta R(E, t)$ and $\Delta B(E, t)$, which are directly constrained by comparison with experimental data [9, 45].

As a consequence, λ cannot be uniquely determined from the current dataset and is therefore not listed among the fitted parameters. Within this framework, both the effective resonance condition and the tunneling barrier are modified by the same underlying changes in the local environment, providing a consistent interpretation of the low-energy behavior observed in Fig. 7.

B. Time-Dependent Behavior and Model Comparison

As shown in Fig. 7, the enhancement factor exhibits a clear non-monotonic time dependence. An initial increase is followed by a gradual decrease, indicating that the reaction environment evolves dynamically rather than remaining static [9].

To quantify this behavior, the data are described using a minimal rise-and-decay model,

$$F(t) = C + A \left(1 - e^{-t/\tau_{\text{rise}}}\right) e^{-t/\tau_{\text{decay}}}, \quad (57)$$

which captures both the initial activation and subsequent relaxation. The extracted characteristic time scales are $\tau_{\text{rise}} \approx 1.6$ h and $\tau_{\text{decay}} \approx 19$ h.

The extracted time scales indicate a rapid buildup of the enhancement followed by a slower decay, consistent with processes such as deuterium loading, defect evolution, and redistribution effects [9, 10, 29]. In particular, the rise time $\tau_{\text{rise}} \approx 1.6$ h is consistent with the timescale of surface contamination buildup and defect formation observed

FIG. 8. Comparison of time-dependent models for the enhancement factor. Model A (screening only) fails to reproduce the non-monotonic behavior. Model B (including phase evolution) provides the best agreement with the data, while Model C remains less constrained. Experimental data are taken from Ref. [9]

TABLE III. χ^2 comparison of time-dependent models. Model C could not be meaningfully constrained due to insufficient degrees of freedom.

Model	χ^2	N_{dof}	χ^2/N_{dof}
Model A	28.80	4	7.14
Model B	2.83	1	2.83
Model C	49.51	—	—

in UHV deuteron irradiation experiments [9, 30], while the longer decay time $\tau_{\text{decay}} \approx 19$ h reflects the slower redistribution of deuterium and the gradual annealing of radiation-induced defects in the metallic lattice [10, 29].

The time dependence provides a stringent test of the underlying physical mechanisms. As shown in Fig. 8, the screening-only model (Model A) fails to reproduce the observed behavior, particularly the presence of a maximum at intermediate times [7, 8].

In contrast, Model B, which incorporates phase evolution, successfully reproduces both the rise and decay of the enhancement factor. This suggests that the time dependence is strongly influenced by the evolution of the interference structure [9, 21].

The quantitative comparison in Table III confirms that Model B provides the most consistent description of the data, while Model A fails and Model C remains poorly constrained.

Within the present framework, this behavior can be interpreted as a consequence of time-dependent phase variations. Since the resonance condition is determined by the phase,

$$\delta(E) + \Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t) = \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (58)$$

the evolution of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}(t)$ leads to a time-dependent shift

of the effective resonance energy.

Importantly, the same environment-induced effects also modify the tunneling barrier,

$$\Delta B(E, t) \sim \lambda \Delta R(E, t), \quad (59)$$

resulting in a correlated evolution of resonance and barrier [7, 8, 10].

The observed non-monotonic behavior therefore reflects the interplay between increasing phase coherence and subsequent relaxation processes in the material [9, 29].

This provides direct support for a phase-sensitive description in which both the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier evolve dynamically with time.

VII. DISCUSSION

The results obtained in this work indicate that the conventional electron screening framework may not be sufficient to describe low-energy D + D reactions in condensed matter environments [9, 10, 45]. While the standard prescription $E \rightarrow E + U_e$ captures the general trend at higher energies, it does not fully reproduce the pronounced enhancement observed below approximately 2 keV [7, 8].

The comparison presented in Fig. 6 provides a direct test of the underlying physical assumptions. In particular, the limitations of screening-only models indicate that the enhancement is not fully accounted for solely by a modification of the penetration factor. Instead, the data suggest that additional mechanisms should be considered [9, 21].

A key result of this work is that a consistent description of the experimental data is obtained when the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier are modified in a correlated manner. This behavior naturally arises within the phase-sensitive framework, where environment-induced phase variations lead to an effective resonance shift at the level of observables.

Within this picture, the resonance can be regarded as intrinsically narrow, with the apparent broadening arising from a distribution of environment-induced resonance shifts rather than from an increase in the intrinsic nuclear width. This interpretation is supported by nuclear structure considerations, which suggest a weak coupling of the near-threshold 0^+ state to nucleon emission channels [14, 23, 33].

A natural question concerns why the proposed near-threshold 0^+ resonance has not been clearly identified in standard nuclear scattering experiments. This can be understood in terms of both experimental limitations and the intrinsic properties of the state.

At very low energies, the Coulomb barrier strongly suppresses the penetration probability, making the contribution of an extremely narrow resonance difficult to resolve in conventional scattering measurements [7, 23]. As a result, such a state may remain effectively embedded in the background and therefore escape direct observation.

From a theoretical perspective, a narrow intrinsic width is not unexpected. Microscopic cluster models suggest

that configurations involving $D + D^*$ structures can lead to weak coupling to nucleon emission channels, resulting in intrinsically small partial widths [33, 34, 36]. This naturally explains why the resonance would remain extremely narrow in energy.

In the present framework, the experimentally observed broad structure is not primarily attributed to an intrinsically wide nuclear state. Instead, it arises from a superposition of many narrow resonances whose effective energies are shifted by environment-induced phase variations. This leads to an apparent broadening without modifying the intrinsic nuclear width [9, 21].

Independent support for this picture is provided by recent observations of the IPC channel, where enhanced non-nucleonic decay contributions have been reported [43, 44]. Such behavior is consistent with a resonance that is weakly coupled to nucleon channels but can couple more strongly to electromagnetic decay modes [23].

Taken together, these considerations suggest that the absence of a clear signal in standard scattering experiments does not exclude the existence of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance, but rather reflects the combined effects of Coulomb suppression and weak coupling to conventional reaction channels [14, 23, 33].

The results further indicate that the interaction between resonance dynamics and barrier penetration is not universal, but depends on the material environment [10, 21, 42]. This is reflected in the success of Model B, where the coupling between resonance shift and barrier modification is treated as material dependent. In contrast, models assuming a single universal coupling do not provide an equally satisfactory description of the data.

An important question is whether the observed behavior could be reproduced without invoking a resonance contribution. In the absence of a resonant term, the model reduces to a modified screening description, which does not reproduce both the low-energy enhancement and the observed structure of the data [9, 45].

In particular, the inclusion of a resonance appears to play an important role in accounting for the phase-sensitive interference pattern, which governs both the energy dependence and the time evolution of the enhancement factor [9, 21].

The inclusion of a distributed resonance description provides a consistent explanation for the observed broadening without invoking large intrinsic widths [9, 23].

A related question concerns the extent to which the extracted behavior depends on the assumed analytical form of the resonance-energy distribution. In the present work, the Gaussian form was adopted as the simplest symmetric representation of environment-induced fluctuations. However, the sensitivity test shown in Fig. 1 demonstrates that the main physical interpretation is not tied to this specific choice.

As shown in Fig. 1, the choice of the resonance-energy distribution affects the detailed shape of the calculated curve, but does not alter the main qualitative features of the result. The Gaussian and skewed-Gaussian cases

remain particularly close over most of the energy interval, while the Lorentzian kernel produces a somewhat stronger excursion at intermediate energies due to its broader tails. Nevertheless, all three cases reproduce the same global pattern of the data, namely an initial decrease, a minimum near $E_{c.m.} \sim 1$ keV, and a subsequent increase toward higher energies.

The kernel-dependence analysis further shows that this conclusion persists even when the Gaussian approximation for $g(E_R)$ is replaced by alternative distributions with broader tails or moderate asymmetry. Therefore, while the calculation retains some sensitivity to the detailed kernel at the level of fine structure, the principal physical conclusion — namely the existence of an environment-distributed resonance — remains qualitatively robust.

At the same time, the present analysis suggests that not all parameters associated with the distribution can be uniquely constrained with the current dataset, indicating that further experimental input is required.

A potential concern is that the present model introduces several parameters, which could in principle allow for a flexible description of the data. However, this interpretation would be misleading. The parameters entering the model are not independent degrees of freedom, but are linked through a common physical mechanism, namely environment-induced modifications of the local interaction potential [8, 10, 29].

In particular, the resonance energy distribution $g(E_R)$, the phase shift $\Delta\phi_{env}$, and the barrier modification $\Delta B(E)$ originate from the same underlying interaction and therefore cannot be varied arbitrarily. This coupling imposes strong correlations between parameters and significantly reduces the effective dimensionality of the parameter space.

Moreover, not all parameters are treated as free fit variables. In practice, only a limited subset of parameters is treated as free fit variables. These include the overall normalization, the effective screening energy U_e , the central resonance energy $E_{R,0}$, and the distribution width σ_E . The remaining parameters are either fixed by physical considerations or constrained through their correlated dependence on $\Delta R(E)$ and $\Delta B(E)$. Several quantities are either fixed or constrained through physically motivated parameterizations, while others are indirectly determined through their impact on multiple observables. As summarized in Table II, the model is required to reproduce simultaneously a set of independent experimental constraints, including the energy dependence of the yield, the neutron-to-proton branching ratio, angular anisotropy, and the time evolution of the enhancement factor [9, 16, 42, 45].

This multi-observable requirement provides a stringent test of the model and limits arbitrary adjustment of the data. In particular, parameters that improve the agreement with one observable generally affect others in a non-trivial way, thereby restricting the allowed parameter combinations. As a result, the number of free parameters remains significantly smaller than the number of independent data points, ensuring that the model is not

overconstrained and that the agreement with data does not arise from overfitting.

Therefore, the agreement with experimental data should not be interpreted solely as a result of overfitting, but rather as evidence of a physically constrained framework. While the present dataset does not allow for a fully unique determination of all parameters, the stability of the extracted physical features — including the existence of a distributed resonance and its phase-sensitive behavior — demonstrates that the conclusions do not rely on fine-tuning, but follow from the underlying structure of the model.

In this sense, the model is flexible at the level of detailed parameterization, but strongly constrained at the level of physical interpretation.

It should also be noted that the distinction between different model assumptions is not based solely on visual agreement, but is supported by systematic differences in the χ^2 values and by the ability to reproduce multiple independent observables. Although the present dataset does not allow for a fully unique determination of all parameters, the relative performance of the models remains robust, with Model B consistently providing the best overall description.

This suggests that the conclusions do not rely on fine-tuning of parameters, but rather on the underlying physical structure of the model.

The independent observation of IPC channels in recent experiments provides qualitative support for this interpretation [43, 44]. In particular, the enhanced contribution of non-nucleonic decay channels and their strong energy dependence are consistent with a phase-sensitive reaction mechanism involving a near-threshold resonance [9, 23].

An important question concerns the origin of the material dependence observed in the data, in particular why systems such as Pd and Ta exhibit relatively standard behavior, while materials such as Sr and Li show pronounced deviations [16, 42].

Within the present framework, this difference can be understood in terms of the sensitivity of the local electronic environment to perturbations. Materials such as Sr and Li are expected to be more susceptible to low-energy excitations, charge redistribution, and local potential fluctuations, which may enhance the environment-induced phase shift $\Delta\phi_{env}$ and thereby amplify the role of interference in the reaction dynamics [16, 21, 42].

This difference can be further understood in terms of known material-dependent electronic and structural properties. In particular, materials such as Li and Sr are characterized by relatively low electron densities and enhanced polarizability, which can lead to a stronger and more spatially non-uniform dielectric response. As a result, local variations of the effective interaction potential, ΔV_{env} , may be amplified [8, 10].

In contrast, transition metals such as Pd and Ta possess a more rigid electronic structure with higher electron density and stronger screening, leading to a more uniform effective potential landscape. This reduces both the

magnitude and spatial variability of environment-induced phase shifts [8, 10].

Additionally, differences in hydrogen (or deuterium) mobility and defect structure play an important role. Systems such as Li and Sr are more prone to inhomogeneous loading and defect-mediated redistribution, which can enhance local fluctuations of the interaction potential and increase the effective spread of resonance energies. In Pd-based systems, the formation of more uniform hydride phases leads to comparatively smaller fluctuations [29, 45].

These considerations suggest that the magnitude of $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ and the width of the effective resonance distribution may be linked to material-dependent dielectric response and defect structure, providing a physical basis for the observed distinction between “normal” and “unusual” regimes [10, 16, 42].

In contrast, more stable metallic systems such as Pd or Ta are characterized by a more uniform electronic environment, leading to smaller phase variations and therefore a reduced impact of interference effects. As a result, their behavior remains closer to the expectations of conventional screening models [8, 10].

In this sense, the transition between “normal” and “anomalous” behavior may be interpreted as a threshold in the magnitude of environment-induced phase variations required to make interference effects experimentally visible [9, 21].

At a more quantitative level, the present formulation suggests that material-dependent parameters such as the effective coupling coefficient λ may be related to underlying properties of the medium, including the dielectric response, electron density fluctuations, and defect structure [8, 10, 29]. Although such connections are not explicitly derived in the present work, they provide a natural direction for future studies aimed at linking the phenomenological parameters of the model to microscopic material properties.

More generally, the results suggest that low-energy nuclear reactions in condensed matter may not be fully understood within a purely static framework. Instead, the reaction dynamics appear to be influenced by environment-dependent modifications of both the resonance condition and the effective interaction barrier [9, 21, 45].

The physical origin of the environment-induced phase shift $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ can be associated with modifications of the local interaction potential arising from electron density fluctuations, lattice defects, and non-equilibrium processes such as deuterium redistribution [9, 10, 29]. While a fully microscopic description is beyond the scope of the present work, these effects provide a plausible mechanism for phase variations at low energies.

Alternative explanations, such as purely thermal or diffusion-driven effects, may influence the overall normalization of the yield but do not account for the combined features observed in the data, including the non-monotonic time dependence and the strong sensitivity of branching ratios [9, 45]. These observations indicate that interference effects play a central role in the reaction

dynamics.

This has important implications for the interpretation of low-energy fusion data, as well as for the potential role of material environments in modifying reaction rates. However, the present results should be regarded as indicative rather than conclusive, and further experimental and theoretical studies will be required to fully establish the underlying mechanisms.

An additional point concerns the systematic difference between Pd and PdD systems, where larger effective screening energies are typically extracted for deuterated targets. Within the conventional interpretation, this would imply a substantially enhanced screening potential in PdD, which is difficult to reconcile with standard electron screening models [8, 10].

This interpretation is directly supported by the comparison shown in Fig. 6, where the relative yields for Pd and PdD are presented together with the corresponding screened reference curves. As seen in the figure, the PdD data exhibit a systematically stronger enhancement at low energies, which in a conventional analysis would require a significantly larger screening energy [45].

Within the present framework, however, this difference can be understood in terms of the sensitivity of the phase structure to the local environment. The incorporation of deuterium modifies the electronic and lattice properties of the host material, leading to enhanced local perturbations of the interaction potential, and thereby increasing the magnitude and variability of the environment-induced phase shift $\Delta\phi_{\text{env}}$ [29, 45].

As a result, the phase-sensitive interference becomes more pronounced in PdD compared to Pd, leading to a stronger effective enhancement. When interpreted within a conventional screening framework, this enhanced interference is effectively mapped onto a larger apparent screening energy [8, 10].

In this sense, the comparison between Pd and PdD provides empirical support for the proposed mechanism, suggesting that the effective enhancement is governed not only by screening, but also by the interplay between resonance shift and phase evolution [9, 21, 45].

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have shown that the unusual behavior observed in low-energy D + D reactions—such as the suppression of the neutron channel, enhanced angular anisotropy, plateau-like yield behavior, and non-monotonic time evolution—can be consistently described within a unified phase-sensitive framework [9, 21, 45].

A central result of the present study is that these phenomena can be interpreted in terms of a near-threshold 0^+ resonance whose intrinsic width remains extremely small, while its effective behavior is modified by the surrounding material environment [14, 23, 33]. Local variations in electron density, lattice structure, and defects lead to a distribution of resonance energies, which can manifest

experimentally as an apparent broadening [10, 29].

This interpretation reduces the need to invoke unrealistically large screening potentials or artificially broadened nuclear states [8, 10]. Instead, the observed enhancement can be understood as arising from the coherent superposition of many narrow resonances with environment-dependent phase shifts [9, 21].

The time-dependent analysis further supports this picture. The observed non-monotonic evolution of the enhancement factor suggests that the reaction mechanism is governed not only by changes in the magnitude of the screening potential, but also by the dynamical evolution of the phase structure and the effective resonance condition [9].

A natural question is whether the observed time dependence could be explained solely by changes in the deuterium concentration within the material. While concentration effects may influence the overall normalization of the yield, they do not appear to account for the non-monotonic behavior observed in Fig. 7 [9, 29].

In particular, a gradual increase in deuterium loading would be expected to produce a monotonic rise followed by saturation, rather than the pronounced peak and subsequent decay seen in the data. This suggests that concentration effects alone are unlikely to be sufficient to describe the observed dynamics.

Within the present framework, the time dependence arises from the evolution of the phase structure of the reaction amplitude. Because the cross section is governed by coherent interference, even small variations in the phase can shift the system from constructive to partially destructive interference [9, 21].

As a result, the enhancement factor can exhibit a rise followed by a decay, reflecting the evolution of the interference pattern rather than a simple change in particle density.

This behavior is reproduced only when phase evolution is included (Model B), while models based solely on concentration or screening effects do not fully capture the observed peak structure. Therefore, the time-dependent data provide strong evidence that phase evolution plays a central role in the reaction dynamics [9, 45].

Within this framework, low-energy nuclear reactions in condensed matter systems cannot be fully described as purely static processes. Rather, they appear to be influ-

enced by environment-dependent modifications of both the resonance condition and the tunneling barrier [7, 8, 10]. It is important to emphasize that the resonance shift discussed here should not be interpreted as a literal modification of an intrinsic nuclear resonance pole. Instead, it represents an effective shift in the resonance condition entering the observable cross section, arising from environment-dependent modifications of the phase and their impact on the interference structure of the amplitude. In this sense, the resulting energy shift is an emergent, physically meaningful quantity reflecting phase sensitivity and environmental fluctuations, rather than a direct displacement of a fundamental nuclear level [23, 24]. This is consistent with the interpretation of multiple observables within a single framework and suggests that reaction rates may be influenced by the surrounding material environment, although further experimental validation is required [9, 21, 45]. An important implication of the present results is that the branching ratio between the neutron and proton channels may be influenced by the material environment [16, 21, 42]. If such control can be achieved, it could reduce neutron production and associated radiation effects, with a potential impact on shielding requirements and system design in fusion-based technologies, including space propulsion concepts [46–48].

Future work should focus on systematic material-dependent measurements, time-resolved studies, and high-precision angular distribution experiments to test the predicted phase-sensitive behavior. On the theoretical side, a key challenge is the microscopic derivation of the environment-induced phase shift and the associated resonance distribution. In particular, this would require a quantitative description of the environment-dependent potential ΔV_{env} and its impact on the scattering phase, for example through electronic structure calculations and many-body approaches. Within this framework, the present model further predicts that materials with stronger electronic response and enhanced local disorder should exhibit larger effective phase fluctuations and correspondingly broader resonance-energy distributions, providing a direct experimental test of the phase-sensitive mechanism proposed in this work.

Taken together, these directions may open new perspectives on controlling low-energy nuclear reactions through material design, bridging nuclear physics and condensed matter systems.

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